

Power position technique prediction model for javelin throws based on a selected Kinematics variable

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Abstract

The present study investigates the correlation between selected kinematic variables and performance outcomes in the javelin throw, with a specific focus on the power position phase. A total of 20 male senior national-level javelin throwers from India, aged between 20 and 28 years, were selected as subjects. The technique of each athlete was captured using sequential photography under controlled conditions, employing calibrated and standardized equipment including a GoPro Hero 5 camera (240 fps), tripod, cones, and measuring tape. Filming was conducted in the sagittal plane to ensure optimal visualization of body movements during the power position. Each athlete performed the javelin throw technique three times, with the best attempt selected for analysis based on expert subjective judgment. The footage was analyzed using Kinovea Software (Version 0.8.27), with frames paused at key moments to extract kinematic variables. The power position technique was assessed by a panel of three expert judges who assigned scores out of 40 for each athlete. Statistical tools including multiple regression analysis, t-values, and partial correlation coefficients were applied to determine the predictive relationship between kinematic variables and performance scores. The level of significance was set at 0.05. The findings indicate a strong predictive value of biomechanical factors related to the, Angle at Left Knee, Angle at Right Hip Joint, Angle at Left Shoulder in optimizing javelin throw performance during the power position phase. It is recommended that training programs for javelin throwers place greater emphasis on biomechanical efficiency and coordination of key joints to enhance overall throwing performance.

Keywords: Javelin throw, power position, biomechanical variables, joint-point method, performance analysis

Introduction

In the javelin throw, the javelin is released at a height of seven feet or more above the surface to which it falls. Since the angle of projection of the 32-38 range in order to attain the greatest distance, is prediction on the fact that the implement projected will not fall below the level from which it was projected (John W. Bunn, 1978) [5]. In the recent years, greater stress has been laid on quality rather than the quantity of training. The coaches and teachers of physical education want their athlete to extract maximum achievement from their training procedures without causing too much strain on them (Rustom N. Sadri,). The aspects of mechanics, biomechanics have revealed the lowest and simplest dependencies in a problem of athletic movement and thus produced the prerequisites for understanding the higher and more complicated form of movements before and further knowledge actually exists. (Gerlord Gochmuth, 1984) [8]. While in the latter events throwing must be from a

circle, the javelin must be discharged from behind the arc of a circle drawn with a radius of 8mt. Such arc shall consist of a strip made of wood or metal.

The role that sports biomechanics widely understood in sports community and the demand for service increasing researchers in sports biomechanics will have to consider carefully how much time they can devote to the provision of scientific services without improving their performances as scholar researchers. To avoid the problems inherent in this situation, it may be necessary to develop programmed of study of the training of technicians in sports biomechanics, who can provide the kind of services sought by sporting bodies. (James G. Hay, 1984) [9]. The center of gravity in the human body is located in the mid of the trunk and at about hip level when standing in the normal erect position with the arm hanging at the side. The change in position of the center of gravity with movement of a body part is instantaneous. External weight added to the body will increase the total

body weight and effect the location of the center of gravity of the body and the added weight. (Fred Wilt, 1960) [14].

Materials and Methods

Selection of Subjects

A total of 20 senior national level athletes were selected as subjects for the purpose of this study. The age range between 20 and 28 years of the subjects. Each participant were informed about the purpose of the study and encouraged to give their best effort during all trials. Prior to participation in the testing procedures, informed consent were obtained from all subjects.

Selection of Variables

Based on literary evidence, correspondence with the expert and scholar’s own understanding and keeping feasibility criterion in mind, the selected variables were as follows:

A. Dependent Variables

- Javelin Throw Technique
- Power Position Technique

B. Independent Variables (Kinematics variables)

- Knee joint
- Hip joint
- Shoulder joint

Technique analysis procedure

Technique of the subjects in Javelin throw (Power position) collected on the basis of the subjective evaluation. The best of 03 times throwing performance on the selected trial were obtained and best techniques of throwing are used for data collection.

Videography Procedure

Videography was employed for the biomechanical analysis of the power position in the javelin throw. A GO PRO HERO 5 camera, operating at 240 frames per second, was positioned on the sagittal plane to capture the movement. The power position during the execution of the javelin throw was selected for detailed analysis. Sequence photographs from the videography were used to create stick figures, which were generated using Kinovea software. These stick figures helped the scholar estimate specific biomechanical variables. Each subject performed the technique three times, and the best trial was selected for analysis. Kinovea software was also used to identify the subject's center of gravity during the throw. The velocity

was determined by analyzing the javelin's flight path immediately after release.

Procedure for Measuring Angular Kinematics

Measured with the aid of Kinovea software, the specified kinematic variables, such as angles at the right hip joint, left shoulder joint and left knee joint, were selected.

Fig 1: Flow chart of Procedure for Measuring Angular Kinematics

Video Protocol

This video control allows you to closely watch a single action in the movie and evaluate the frame of the movement by frame in slow motion because Kinovea operates nearly any file natively. Kinovea has had variously incredible, interesting, and diverse aspects, such as analysis, measurement, comparison, and observations.

Fig 2: Throwing power position of the subject.

Statistical Procedure

The multiple regression analysis, t-values, and partial correlations were used in order to find out the prediction of power position technique in javelin throw based on kinematic variables. For testing the hypothesis, the level of significance was set at 0.05.

Table 1: Relationship of selected angular kinematic variable with performance of subjects in javelin throw.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.864 ^a	.747	.733	1.013	.747	53.051	1	18	.000
2	.913 ^b	.833	.814	.846	.087	8.816	1	17	.009
3	.938 ^c	.880	.857	.740	.047	6.217	1	16	.024

Table-1 show the model, with a value of R² of .880, is best for finding regression equations since it produces the most R-squared. It can be seen from Table 3 that in the third model, three independent variables namely, Angle at Left Knee Joint, Angle at Right Hip Joint, Angle at Left Shoulder have been identified and therefore, the regression

equation shall be developed using these three variables only. The R² value for this model is .880, and therefore, these three independent variables explain 88% variations in score of Javelin Power Position Technique. Thus, this model can be considered appropriate to develop the regression equation.

Table 2: Variable Regression Coefficients, t-values, and Partial Correlations of Javelin Power Position Technique

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-8.814	5.546		-1.589	.129
	Angle of Left Knee	.241	.033	.864	7.284	.000
2	(Constant)	-12.810	4.823		-2.656	.017
	Angle of Left Knee	.181	.034	.649	5.280	.000
	Angle of Right Hip Joint	.103	.035	.365	2.969	.009
3	(Constant)	-16.975	4.538		-3.741	.002
	Angle of Left Knee	.208	.032	.748	6.526	.000
	Angle of Right Hip Joint	.096	.031	.338	3.131	.006
	Angle of Left Shoulder	.013	.005	.233	2.493	.024

In the third model, all three regression coefficients, t-values are significant because their p-values are less than 0.05. Thus, it might be concluded that the variables Angle at Left Knee Joint, Angle at Right Hip Joint, and Angle at Left Shoulder Joint, comprehensively describe the differences in the Javelin Power Position Technique of throwing in athletics.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The linear and angular kinematic variables i.e., Angle at Left Knee, Angle at Right Hip Joint, Angle at Left Shoulder would help to javelin power position technique for chosen javelin Athletes.
2. The linear and angular kinematic variables i.e., Angle at Left Knee should be blocked (straight) in javelin power position technique selected javelin athletes.
3. The linear and angular kinematic variables i.e. Angle at Right Hip Joint, when the right hip joint moves in the forward direction it helps in apply the maximum force upon javelin.
4. The linear and angular kinematics variables i.e. javelin power position time Angle at Left Shoulder down so that we can maximum reach the javelin.
5. Kinematics variables should be used to develop the javelin power position technique of javelin players and allows players to progress towards an excellent performance of javelin power position.
6. The model of the javelin power position technique provided a structure for analysis to enhance the javelin performance.

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